

The Study Of Important Mathematical Applications Of Ancient India

Swapnil Ramesh Gadhawe

Researcher (RTMNU, Nagpur) Vinoba Nagar Near Rajaram Launs, Tumsar Dist. Bhandara

Email- swapnilgadhawe007@gmail.com

Abstract:

In all ancient civilizations, the first expression of mathematical knowledge appears in the form of a calculation system. In very early societies, numbers were represented by a set of lines. Later, however, different numbers came to be represented by specific numerical names and symbols, for example in India. In places such as Rome, they were called alphabets, but not all numbers in ancient civilizations were based on the decimal system. Records of mathematical activities in the Vedic period are mostly found in the Vedas along with religious rituals. As in many other agriculturally based ancient civilizations, the study of arithmetic and geometry was also inspired by secular activities. Thus, to some extent, old mathematical advances developed in India in the same way as in Egypt, Babylon, and China. Philosophical theories profoundly influenced the development of mathematical hypotheses and axioms. Like the Upanishads' view of the world, space and time were considered infinite in Jain's philosophy. This led to a strong interest in the definitions of very large numbers and infinitesimals. In this research paper, important mathematical applications of ancient India have been studied.

Keywords: Ancient Civilization, Mathematical Hypothesis, Mathematical Activity, Mathematical Application, Arithmetic Function.

Research Methodology:

The research paper has depended on secondary data.

Objective of Research:

- 1) To study the important Mathematical Applications of Ancient India.
- 2) To study the history of important Mathematical Applications of Ancient India.

Introduction:

The decimal system existed in India during the Harappan period, as evidenced by the analysis of Harappan weights and measures. Weights with ratios of 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, and 500 have been identified from that period. Scales with decimal divisions have also been found. One special feature of Harappan weights and measures that attracts attention is their accuracy. A bronze rod with ghats in units of 0.367 inches indicates the degree of accuracy demanded by the time. Records of mathematical activities in the Vedic period are mostly found in the Vedas along with religious rituals. Nevertheless, as in many other agriculturally based ancient civilizations, the study of arithmetic and geometry was also inspired by secular activities. Thus, to some extent, ancient mathematical advances developed in India in the same way as in Egypt, Babylon, and China. The land distribution system and the assessment of agricultural tax required accurate measurement of the agricultural area. When there was a redistribution of

land, their consolidation, then there was a problem of land measurement, whose solution was necessary, thus mathematics was useful in the services of both secular activity and ritual.

Arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, square, cube, and moola are described in the Narada Vishnu Purana. Its pioneer is considered to be Ved Vyas who lived in 1000 BC. Had happened Examples of Geometry / Line Mathematics / Science 800 BC. In Baudhayana's Shulva Sutra and 600 B.C. Apastamba Sutra describes the technique of construction of the ritualistic sacrificial altar used in the Vedic period. These texts may have used geometrical knowledge acquired in an earlier period, possibly in the Harappan period. Baudhayan's formula shows information about basic geometric shapes and how to convert one geometric shape into another isosceles shape or its fraction or its multiple.

Philosophical theories profoundly influenced the development of mathematical hypotheses and axioms. Like the Upanishads' view of the world, space and time were considered infinite in Jain's philosophy. This led to a great interest in the definitions of very large numbers and infinitesimals. Infinite numbers were created through recursive formulas. The same was done in Anuyogadwara Sutra. Jain mathematicians told five types of infinite numbers, which include infinite in one direction, infinite in

two directions, infinite in area, infinite everywhere, and infinite continuously. 3rd century BC In the Bhagavati Sutras composed in 2nd century B.C. The permutation combination listed in the Sthananga Sutra composed in Jain set theory probably arose parallel to Syadvad of Jain epistemology, in which reality is described as state-pairs and state-change pairs of truth. Buddhist literature also shows an awareness of indefinite and infinite numbers. Buddhist mathematics was classified into 'ganana' i.e. simple mathematics or 'sankhyana' i.e. higher mathematics. Indian numerals developed into their modern form between the 7th and 11th centuries and became the foundation stone of modern mathematical symbols, with symbols representing various mathematical operations such as plus, minus, square root, etc.

Bhaskar-I handled the incomplete work of Aryabhata and elaborated on topics such as longitude of planets, relation of planets to each other and luminous constellations, rising and setting of planets and moon phase. These studies required more advanced mathematics. So Bhaskara elaborated the trigonometric equations introduced by Aryabhata and reached the correct conclusion like Aryabhata that pi is an irrational number. It is his most important contribution. The astrologer mathematician Varahamihira was born in Ujjain in the 6th century CE who co-wrote earlier written books on mathematical astrology and extended Aryabhata's corpus of trigonometric formulas. His works on permutations and combinations complemented the achievements of the Jain mathematicians on the subject and gave a method of finding the pressure value that is very similar to the modern "Pascal's Triangle".

In the 7th century, Brahmagupta did the important work of cataloging the fundamentals of algebra. In addition to listing the algebraic properties of zero, he also listed the algebraic properties of negative numbers. His work on the solution of quadratic indeterminate equations foreshadowed the work of Euler and Lagrange. Aryabhata's equations were explained in detail by Manjula in the 10th century and Bhaskaracharya in the 12th century. Bhaskaracharya derived the value of the derivative of the sine function. Later mathematicians used their unique

understanding of integration to calculate the area of curved planes and the volume enclosed by curved planes. This period also saw developments in applied mathematics – trigonometric tables and units of measurement were created. Yatibrishabha's Tiloyapannati, composed in the 6th century, gives various units for the measurement of time and distance, and also describes a system of measurement of infinite time.

By the end of the 12th century, the Muslim conquest of India had begun. With this began the decay of the Indian initiative in the positive sciences. The little originality that remained in India after the decline of the Mughal rule was suppressed by contact with western civilization. Thus India has been passing through a gloom for the last six centuries, from which it is now recovering and trying to make a new synthesis of its ancient civilization with the achievements of modern culture.

The Important Mathematical Applications of Ancient India:

Mathematics in India has its roots in Vedic literature which is about 4000 years old. 1000 BC and 1000 A.D. Various concepts of mathematics were given by Indian mathematicians. These included for the first time the concept of zero, techniques of algebra and algorithms, square roots, and cube roots. There are various examples of mathematics from ancient India which are applicable even today. If the Indian mathematician and astronomer Aryabhata had not been there, the number would not have been zero. Although people have always understood the concept of being nothing or being nothing. A comparatively new concept, it was fully developed in India around the fifth century. Before this, mathematicians had struggled to perform even the simplest arithmetical calculations. Today, zero both as a symbol (or number) and as a concept means the absence of any quantity. Zero allows us to navigate, perform complex equations, and invent computers. "Zero is widely seen as one of the greatest innovations in human history, a cornerstone of modern mathematics and physics," said Peter Gobets, secretary of the ZeroGrindia Foundation or Zero Project. In ancient India, traditional mathematics called ganitam was known before the development of algebra, it originated from the name bijaganitam, which was given to the

algebraic form of calculation. *Ka* means second and *Ganitam* means.

Around the 5th century in India, a system of mathematics simplified sagotic calculations. At that time its application was limited to astronomy because its forerunners were astronomers. Since astronomical calculations are complex and involve many variables that go into the derivation of unknown quantities. Algebra is a trivial method of calculation and by this attribute, it scores higher than traditional arithmetic. Trigonometry originated in ancient India. It traveled from India to the Middle East and was adopted by people everywhere. From here it was conveyed to Europe through the Arabs and went through several modifications to reach its present form. Trigonometry was considered a portion of astronomy in ancient times. Historians consider Aryabhata, Brahmagupta, Bhaskara, and Bhaskara 11 as the main exponents of trigonometry, Bhaskara. 1 gave formulas to find the values of the sine function for angles greater than 900 (Aust's angle), on the other hand, Bhaskara 11 gave exact expressions to calculate the trigonometric ratios of acute angles such as 180, 360, 540, and 20 Gave.

In the classical period of Indian mathematics (400 CE to 1600 CE), significant contributions were made by scholars such as Aryabhata, Brahmagupta, Mahavira, Bhaskara 11, Madhava of Sangamgram, and Nilakantha Somayaji. The decimal number system in use around the world today was first recorded in Indian mathematics. It was in the 7th century CE when Brahmagupta found the first general formula for solving quadratic equations, the decimal system (or Hindu number system), which was the forerunner of the Arabic numerical system, originated in India and developed between the 6th century CE Had happened. The Fibonacci sequence is a series of numbers where a number is found by adding two numbers before it, starting at 0 and going through 0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, and so on. It was first described by Virhanka, Gopat, and Hemchandra as an outbreak in the earlier writings of Pingala. Made of ivory, the rulers found during excavations revealed amazing precision of decimal subdivisions on it. The people of the Indus civilization realized great accuracy in measuring mass, length, and time. He was among the first to

develop a system of uniform weights and measures. A comparison of the available items indicates a large scale of variation across the Indus regions. Their smallest division, marked on the scale from ivory found at Lothal in Gujarat, was about 1.704 mm, the smallest division ever recorded on the Bronze Age scale. The history of measurement systems in India begins in the early Indus Valley Civilization, which survives samples dating to the 5th millennium BCE. The adoption of standard weights and measures from early times is visible in the country's architectural, folk, and metallurgical artifacts. A complex system of weights and measures was adopted by the Mauryan Empire (322–185 BCE), which also made rules for the use of this system. Later, the Mughal Empire (1526–1857) used standard measures to determine land holdings and collect land tax as part of the Mughal land reforms. A total of 558 weights were excavated from Mohenjodaro, Harappa, and Chanhu-daro, not including the defective weights they found no statistically significant difference between weights that were excavated from five different layers. The depth of each was about 1.5 meters. This was indication that strong control existed for at least 500 years. A weight of 13.7 g is one of the units used in the Indus Valley. The notation was based on the binary and decimal systems. 83% of the weights of the diggers from the above three cities were cubic and 68% were made of rags.

Indian mathematicians also contributed to the field of geometry. There was a field of mathematical applications called *Rekha Ganita* (line calculation). The *Sulva Sutras*, which means 'the rule of law', gives geometrical methods for building altars and temples. The layout of the temples was called *Mandala*. Some important works in this area have been done by Apastamba, Bodhayana, Hiranyakeshin, Varaha, and Vadhula. Mathematicians from Kerala devised rules for second-order interpolation to calculate intermediate sine values. Madhava, a mathematician from Kerala, may have discovered the sine and cosine series about three hundred years before Newton. In this sense, we can consider Madhava as the founder of mathematical analysis. Madhava (circa 1340 - 1425 A.D.) was the first to take decisive steps in the treatment of its boundary-transcendence from finite

processes to infinity of ancient Indian mathematics.

Binary numbers were discovered in the West by the German mathematician Gottfried Leibniz in 1695. However, new evidence proves that binary numbers were used in India before the 2nd century, more than 1500 years before their discovery in the West. The source of this discovery is a text on music by Pingala titled "Chhandasastra" which means the science of meter. This text falls under the category of "sutras" or aphoristic sayings. A detailed discussion of these brief but profound statements is to be found in later comments. The descent of "Chhandshastra" has been done in the second century.

Conclusion:

Many mathematical concepts emerged in India, such as the number system, decimal system, and the use of zero, square root, and cube root. Brick construction and vertical intersection of roads in the Indus Valley Civilization, the Monolithic Pillars of Ashoka, and the Shulbasutras (the concept of acute and obtuse angles) show extensive knowledge of measurement and geometry. ' (Indian numeral), which is currently known as Arabic. It was used in the inscriptions of Ashoka. The concept of zero has its basis in the Indian philosophical concept called 'Shunya'. Aryabhata calculated the area of a triangle. As a result of which trigonometry was born. Seeing the genius of ancient Indian mathematicians for the use of mathematics in ancient Indian art, let us wake up our dormant talent and bring it to the fore, to join India as a leading country before the world. Contribute to it. Some of the other such mathematicians have been born in India in modern times and spread India's identity like the light of a firefly. the way we use the same identity We have to make it, only then the usefulness and significance of mathematics will be possible for us. Today's youth, carrying forward the tradition developed by our ancient Indian mathematicians, should try to establish mathematics back in the same place in India. By remembering the use of mathematics in ancient Indian art, knowing, understanding, and developing in mathematics, get the same pride.

Reference:

1. Morris Kline, *Mathematical Thought from Ancient to Modern Times*, Volume 2, OUP USA; Revised ed. Edition (1999)
2. Morris Kline, *Mathematical Thought from Ancient to Modern Times*, Volume 1, OUP USA; Illustrated edition (1990)
3. T.A. Sarasvati Amma, *Geometry in Ancient and Medieval India*, Motilal Banarsidass,; 2nd Edition (2017)
4. T.S. Bhanumurthy, *A Modern Introduction To Ancient Indian Mathematics*, New Age International Private Limited (2008)
5. Runu Dhar, Debadatta Adak, *New Thoughts on Ancient and Modern Mathematics*, EBH Publishers India; 1st Edition (2021)
6. <http://hinduonline.co/DigitalLibrary/SmallBooks/HinduMathematics2Eng.pdf>
7. <https://www.davidhbailey.com/dhbtalks/dhb-india-2017.pdf>
8. <https://publications.azimpremjiuniversity.edu.in/600/1/Ancient%20India%20and%20Mathematics2010IssueXIV.pdf>
9. <https://www.encyclopedia.com/science/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/mathematics-medieval-india>
10. <https://math.illinoisstate.edu/schebol/teaching/320-10-files/Amartya.pdf>
11. <http://ancientindianwisdom.com/contribution-to-science-overview/contributions-to-science/development-in-mathematics>
12. <https://gonitsora.com/a-brief-history-of-ancient-indian-mathematics-part-i/>
13. <https://www.cerc.utexas.edu/~jay/anc.html>
14. https://www.tifr.res.in/~archaeo/FOP/FoP%20papers/ancmathsources_Dani.pdf
15. https://www.isical.ac.in/~amartya/overview_motherindia.pdf
16. <https://www.igntu.ac.in/eContent/IGNTU-eContent-378558069426-BA-AIHC-6-DrJanardhanaB-ScienceandTechnologyinAncientIndia-3.pdf>
17. https://www.mathunion.org/fileadmin/IMU/ICM2010/offline/www.icm2010.in/wp-content/icmfiles/uploads/JLNehru_final.pdf
18. https://namami.gov.in/sites/default/files/book_pdf/History%20and%20Development%20of%20Mathematics%20in%20India.pdf
19. <https://www.historydiscussion.net/history-of-india/contribution-of-ancient-india-towards-science-and-mathematics/2267>